

THE SEMANTIC FEATURES OF DETACHED CONSTRUCTION IN ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14738659>

Abstract: This article examines the detached construction as a stylistic phenomenon in linguistics, which is one of the topical issues for the stylistics direction of linguistics. Language phenomena in English and Uzbek are directly related to language and speech issues. It is in this respect that the phenomenon of the detached construction has its own characteristics in language matters. A detachment is a linguistic phenomenon, a speaker's unintended but additionally stated afterthought. It expands, realizes, completes and clarifies the content of the main expression of the previous sentence. By means of this phenomenon, in the course of the conversation, an explanation that is left incomplete in the main sentence and is considered extremely necessary to be said can be filled. In the process of studying the detached construction, it became clear that its relationship with a number of similar phenomena in linguistics, the similarities and differences between them, are the cause of certain discussions. This article discusses some of the new features of the detached construction. The formal features of detachments are different from each language. We identify all of the detachment in the literary texts.

Key words: Detached constructions, semantic feature, stylistic phenomena, typology.

1 Introduction

In English, the issue of detachment is very little studied. Grammarians are limited to superficially mentioning the existence of this type of connection between sentences, but detachment are also a special type of combining simple sentences into complex sentences.

A detached construction can include situations of different categories, namely: time, place, purpose, course of action, measure, degree, quantity, etc. You've got to stay here and help me with the farm, Roy.

"Detachment is the addition of additional messages and explanations to the main statement through a conjunction."

"Detachment device is a type of syntactic connection, which consists of separating some part of a simple or complex sentence, including intonation-semantic separation, additional message, comment, explanation."

As a result of connecting the sentences through the suffix, a complex syntactic integrity-detachment device is formed.

Supplementary construction - "a complex sentence or a type of complex syntactic unity consisting of two or more logical clauses". The detached construction consists of a main (main) sentence and a connecting part that provides additional information.

"Parts of the detached structure are constructively welded to each other, so that one of them is a continuation of the other and has a property that cannot be used separately"

L.V. Shcherba explains the detachment as follows:

1) The detachment is a kind of clarification of some idea of the main part: I'm fighting for my happiness For Royers.

2) The detachment reveals the meaning of the word in the main clause, it has a general meaning: I think. I shall write an account.

3) The detachment is the result of the development of thought that occurs as a result of some kind of reflection: These shoes are wrong. Devilish

4) The detachment cannot appear unexpectedly.

V.V. According to Gavrilova, the classification proposed by L.V. Shcherba is clearly formulated and justified, but does not indicate the real reason for the appearance of detachments in speech. "The appearance of detachment constructions in speech is often explained by the internal state of the speaker" According to the author, the detachment occurs unintentionally as an addition to what has already been said in the speech. With the desire of the authors to bring written speech closer to the norms of oral speech, the detachment is widely introduced in written speech.

According to the author, the detachment arises from special communicative purposes: adding to the sentence, clarifying what was said before, repeating what was said before to emphasize something important. To these thoughts M.E. Shafiro reacts as follows. According to him, detachment is a typical category of conversational syntax.

This means that the detachment should be seen not as a violation of syntactic norms, but as a type of typified form of sentences in colloquial speech, a special structural type that does not imply a violation of the norms of "full" sentences at all through their abstractly expressed grammatical scheme emphasizes.

2 Technology for obtaining materials and research method

V.V. Gavrilova's opinion about the detachment construction, that is, the typical feature of the detachment construction is that it appears involuntarily in speech. With the help of this connection, individual words, phrases, sentences that were not originally intended, but appeared during or after the utterance of the previous element, are attached.

M. E. Shafiro defined constructions as "a word or phrase that is clearly connected grammatically and syntactically with the main clause and is perceived as its member, taken as isolated as possible, which gives them great syntactic weight and expression." They looked slyly into her eyes. There was laughter in them. And love."

In this example, there is a separation of clauses, not a detachment. D.T. According to Tuyakova, this case distinguishes a special type among detachment devices, that is, "linking constructions representing the intonationally and meaningfully distinguished part of the sentence".

Leave off. Now.

I've spoken him. For some minutes.

Here is M.E. Shafiro and D.T. Tuyakova considers the detachment to be simply a separation from the main clause, which were once part of the sentence. And these concepts should not be confused.

3 Experimental results and their discussion

While we are studying detached construction and their use in artistic texts, Studies have shown that the detachment device can add parts of existing sentences to the main sentence using connectors, related words and intonation: 1) I gave her a great help. But I couldn't stay in her world any longer. (John Brain) 2) He has a power, and not a little. (John Brain) 3) Your rooms are entirely your own. And you must bring your friends any time you like. (John Brain) 4) The rain has stopped, and it was very quiet in the house. It doesn't do you justice, though. Is it Beryl? (John Brain) 5) I wasn't aware of these facts until much later, of course, I thought Bob and Eva were immensely sophisticated. (John Brain)

A comma, semi-colon, period is used in the conjunction case, and a period and a semi-colon are used in the non-conjunction case.

Modern English is characterized by:

1) Detachment with connecting and linking words: Why shouldn't I call at the house? And why should I? (John Brain)

He's always so much aware of what he's doing than you think. (John Brain)

This type of detachment is characterized by the use of conjunctions "and", "even", and even", "and as", "but not".

He'll throw things away. But not without some sort of regret. (John Brain)

2) Connecting the detachment constructions with coordinating connectors. It should be noted that the conjunctions "and" and "but" are often used in the auxiliary part of sentences with a detachment device: He was good-looking. And he was also charming

In this example, the conjunction "and" forms an independent sentence, separated by a period, it performs a connecting function, increases the focus on the character in the text and gives more emphasis to the idea about him.

There are also additional devices that connect with connecting "or". It's cottage simplicity somehow suited her better: or better what Joe had started to like in her.

This example clearly shows the detachment function of the conjunction "or". The author seems to have analyzed Joe's attitude towards the girl. The rustic simplicity of the people suited him better, or rather Joe began to like it. The author identifies and explains the characteristic of Suzanne's character that the hero likes.

Opposite coordinating conjunctions indicate opposite meanings: The smile which accompanied it took the sting from the rebuke; but I was aware that she was in control of the conversation. (John Brain)

3) In addition to the study of detachment devices, it is possible to meet constructions with subordinate connections. Analyzing this relationship, the detachment device has more coordination relationship than the main part: 1) Perhaps that isn't entirely true. Perhaps I wasn't directed in the Minister of Labor. 2) It was the kind gesture which only a virgin could have gotten away with. Because it was so natural and unstudied it moved me almost to tears. 3) It didn't choose the house. Although I think it's a very pleasant one. 4) But lost, like a little girl. As if you were looking for something. 5) I took her at her face value. Which is the last thing that any woman wants.

From this point of view, it is permissible to say that with the help of conjunctions with adverbs, cause, condition, consequence, comparison, conjunction, i.e., synonymous relationships with complex sentence parts can be shown through the detachment device.

4) Detachment devices without connectors:

I was talking with her as freely as I would with Charles; the realization was rather disconcerting.

A girl from his office. Young and plump and dump.

It can be seen that the attached part of this detachment devices is connected to the main part by intonation during pronunciation and by means of periods or semicolons in writing.

They are very expressive: You're just bodies. Very fine bodies.

Detachment constructions are found in colloquial speech and literary texts. These models are characterized by sharp thoughts and a fast pace of narration: I don't think he'd play anymore if I left. It would kill him / Literally. /

In English, the detachment divides the semantics of constructions into two groups:

1) The appended part contains the extension of the previous thought: Who wants it? I want... Emma wants... We want.

2) Detachment constructions that express the attitude of limiting, narrowing, emphasizing or clarifying the previous idea

We'll leave the others behind. Just you and me.

The attached section clarifies the subject.

In addition, there are additional constructions that come in order to express an additional idea:

Zombies always pass away or cross the Great Divide or go into the sunset.

And they lose people like a parcel or a glove. And they can't bear to talk about it or to be reminded of it.

This type of detachment models develops in the main sentence, completes the expressed idea, it gradually shows further actions. The result is a fully dynamic structure.

In the analysis of the literary text in English, detachments can also be found for the purpose of modification in the text: He just throws pounds of money at us. A thousand pounds. Sometimes, three. This app provides more accurate or reliable device information.

Another semantic feature of the detachment in English is that the detachment "sums up" the idea expressed in the main part: He said it. They said it. Everyone said it.

4 Conclusions

So, although the English language has not yet been fully studied, there is an detachment device. Its semantics is similar to the Uzbek language, mainly as an detachment to the previous sentence represents a complementary, explanatory meaning. The scope of detachment constructions can extend beyond a single sentence. With the help of the attached part, it is possible not only to provide additional information, but also to express one's reaction to the expressed opinion. According to Galperin, in English, the detachment device is called "cumulation", while in other sources, "detached construction" is still being studied as "parcellation". But when these different nomenclatures and views are explored, in English it is more appropriate to call the detachment a "detached construction". This is because the term "cumulation" is more specific to other fields than linguistics, while "parcellation" is treated as another phenomenon similar to, but at the same time different from, the detachment device in linguistics. So, it can be said that a complete opinion has not yet been confirmed in this regard. These are the opinions expressed about the interpretation of the detachment device in English, the similarities and dissimilarities of its formal and semantic features to the Uzbek language. In each language, the detachment was studied and analyzed in its own way.

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